

WELL-POSEDNESS OF THE LOCAL QP PROBLEM

In the proposed splitting framework, the update associated with the local engineering constraints is reduced to a sequence of small stage-wise quadratic programs. These local problems enforce guide-vane rate limits and other operating constraints through the feasible set \mathcal{C}_i , while the quadratic objective penalizes the deviation from the corresponding reference variable generated by the ADMM iteration. Since the feasibility of \mathcal{C}_i is ensured by the prescribed operating ranges around the nominal point, the remaining issue is to verify convexity and uniqueness of the local solution. The following proposition establishes that the local QP is well posed.

Proposition 1.

Suppose that the local feasible set \mathcal{C}_i is nonempty for each stage i . Then \mathcal{C}_i is a closed convex polyhedral set. Moreover, the local quadratic program is strictly convex and therefore admits a unique minimizer.

Proof:

Let $\zeta_i^{(1)}, \zeta_i^{(2)} \in \mathcal{C}_i$, and let $\theta \in [0,1]$. Then one has

$$A_i \zeta_i^{(1)} \leq b_i, \quad A_i \zeta_i^{(2)} \leq b_i \quad (1)$$

By affine linearity, the convex combination satisfies

$$A_i (\theta \zeta_i^{(1)} + (1-\theta) \zeta_i^{(2)}) \leq \theta b_i + (1-\theta) b_i = b_i \quad (2)$$

Therefore, \mathcal{C}_i is convex. The set \mathcal{C}_i is also closed because it is defined by finitely many affine inequalities. Moreover, \mathcal{C}_i is polyhedral because all defining constraints are affine.

The objective function of the local quadratic program can be expanded as

$$f_i(\zeta_i) = \frac{1}{2} \zeta_i^T \zeta_i - \bar{\zeta}_i^T \zeta_i + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\zeta}_i^T \bar{\zeta}_i \quad (3)$$

The Hessian matrix of $f_i(\zeta_i)$ is the identity matrix.

$$\nabla^2 f_i(\zeta_i) = I \quad (4)$$

Equation above implies that the objective function is strictly convex. Since the feasible set \mathcal{C}_i is convex, the local problem is a strictly convex quadratic program. Therefore, whenever $\mathcal{C}_i \neq \emptyset$, the minimizer is unique.

This result confirms that the guide-vane rate constraints and other local engineering limits do not destroy convexity. They only modify the geometry of the local feasible set. Hence, the proposed splitting framework separates the global dynamic coupling from local constraint enforcement while retaining a well-posed sequence of subproblems.